

**The Effect of Elaboration-Based Learning Method and Motivation Toward
English Learning Outcomes**

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Abstrack

This study aimed to examine the effect jointly or partially between Elaboration Base-Learning Method and Motivation toward First Grade Sudents' English Learning Outcomes of Alfajar Yunior High School, Bekasi Eastern Jakarta, Indonesia. This research is an experimental study. The target population was all first gade, consisting 75 students as well as the research sample. The instrument used to retrieve the data is treated Elaboration Based-Learning Method, Conventional Method, Motivation and test results to learn English. The resulting data were analyzed using a statistical program SPSS 20.0 and inferential analysis of a two-lane ANOVA to test the hypothesis . The results showed 1) There were significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who taught by using the Elaboration Based-Learning Method to Conventional Method. 2) There were significant differences between students who have a high motivation taught by using the Elaboration Based-Learning Method and with Conventional Method. 3) There were significant differences between students who have a low motivation taught by using the Elaboration Based-learning Method and with ConventionalMethod, 4) There was no interaction effect between Elaboration Based-Learning Method and Motivation towards learning outcomes, however, there was a partial interaction effect between teaching methods with learning outcomes and motivation to learn English with English's learning outcomes. Based on these findings it can be concluded that the sufficiently effective Elaboration Based-Learning Method to improve English learning outcomes .

Keywords: Elaboration Based Learning Method, Motivation, Learning Outcomes

A. Introduction

The emergence of several current learning methods is an attempt to improve learning, especially English. One is the elaboration based learning method. In the process of learning by using this method the problem of English will be solved. Besides in learning English is the teacher explains, while the students listen, it will be replaced by a new paradigm that students actively construct the knowledge, the teacher as a facilitator (help), so that the students will get the concept of English clearly and correctly.

Elaboration based-learning model is a learning that adds additional ideas based on what a student already knew. This learning used effectively if the concept and structure added according to the principle of inference. The implication of this learning strategy is to encourage students to explore the information, for example, to draw conclusions and speculate about the possible implications, Elaboration method is only concerned with organizational strategy at the macro level (Reigeluth, 1983).

This method started teaching by providing an explanation of a general nature, simple, basic but not abstract. This method also describes the use of a series prerequisite from the simple to more complex, and provides an overview and conclusion in a systematic way. Important part that relates to the subject matter. The concept of learning prerequisite includes the fact that knowledge must be obtained before other knowledge acquired. A set of learning called learning hierarchy prerequisite

This research attempts to discuss the elaboration based learning method as a method that can provide a new vehicle for educators and learners in the implementation of learning. The implications of this learning method will encourage students to explore the information that generates insight and their knowledge horizon. In addition to the selection of appropriate learning method, teachers and students demanded to determine its success in the process of English learning.

Students' motivation is one of the internal factors that is important for the development of students in the study effectively referring to the expected goals. Motivation to learn is a principle of learning which is based on the activities and responsibilities of the students themselves to succeed in learning. Students are expected to have a high desire to learn, so that it can reach higher learning outcomes. Slameto (2003) stated motivation to learn is the attitude of the students to always have the will to face the problems of English learning.

Based on the above background, the researchers tried to study on the Effect of Elaboration Based-Learning Model and Student Motivation on Students' English Learning Outcomes

B. Problem formulation

Based on the background of the problem, then in this study problem formulation as follows:

- 1) Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between

students who taught by using the Elaboration learning-based method to conventional.

2) Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who have a high motivation taught by using the Elaboration based-learning method and with conventional.

3) Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who have a low motivation taught by using the Elaboration based-learning method and with conventional?.

4) Is there no interaction effect between elaboration based learning method and motivation towards English learning outcomes?.

C. Theoretical study

1. Definition of Motivation

The word "motive" is defined as efforts that encourage someone to do something. As Sardiman (1990) said in his book *Understanding Psychology of Human Behavior* quoted in Purwanto (1998): motif is the behavior or actions of a goal or incentive. While Nasution (1995) said that motives are all power encourage someone to do something. motivation is the desire or impulse that arises in a person consciously or unconsciously to perform a task with a specific purpose.

According to Sabri (2001) motivation is anything that drives behavior that requires or encourages people to meet a need. Meanwhile, according to Wahjosumidjo (1987) motivation is a psychological process that reflects the interaction between the attitudes, needs, perceptions, and decisions that occur in a person to behave in order to meet the felt needs.

Furthermore, Purwanto (1998) argued that the motivation is driving a conscious effort to influence a person's behavior that he be moved to action to do something to reach outcome or purpose. There are two kinds of motivations, namely intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Motivation has intrinsic in a person according to his needs. This motivation does not require stimulation. While extrinsic motivation arises due to the stimulation from outside of individuals.

Types of motivation according to (Winkel, 1986) consists of :

- a. Motivation or organic needs, including the need to drink, eat, breathe, sexual act, and needs to rest. This is in accordance with the Frandsen types of physiological drives.
- b. Emergency Motivation. This includes in this type of motif, among others: the urge to save him, the urge to retaliate, to strive, to hunt. This motivation arises due to stimulation from the outside.
- c. Objective Motivation. This concerns the need for exploration, manipulation, to gain interest. These motivation appears as a boost to be able to face the outside world reactively.

According to Frandsen, as cited by Sadirman (1990) that still add other types of motivations as follows:

- a. Cognitive Motivation. This Motivation shows the intrinsic symptoms, namely the individual satisfaction. Individual satisfaction is a human

being and usually intangible. This type of Motivation is very primary in learning activities, particularly with intellectual development.

- b. Self-expression. Personal appearance is part of human behavior. The important thing was not just the individual needs to know why and how things happen, but also able to create an event. This is necessary for creativity, imagination. So in this case the person has a desire for self-actualization.
- c. Self-enhancement. Through self-actualization and development competencies will enhance the progress of one's self. Elevation and advancement became one desire for every individual. In learning can be created competency healthy atmosphere for students to achieve a feat.

It can be concluded that motivation is a drive or drives contained in man which can lead, direct, and organize behavior. This is related to efforts to meet the perceived needs, both physical needs and spiritual needs. In relation to the learning activity, the motivation to learn means that the overall driving force in the learners who can lead, guarantee, and provide direction on learning activities, in order to achieve the expected learning objectives. With the motivation to learn, the students can have intensity and continuity in the process of learning.

2. Elaboration Based-Learning Method

Elaboration based learning method is learning that adds additional ideas based on what a person has already known before. Elaboration is to associate the item to be remembered with something else, such as a phrase, scene, scenery, places, or stories. According Degeng (1989), Elaboration theory is a theory that prescribes teaching by following the general sequence to detail. The general order begins by displaying the epitome (structural fill subject areas studied) and then elaborates on the parts that exist within the epitome in more detail. Context is always shown with the synthesis shown gradually. According to Reigeluth, et al (1983) elaboration of teaching using the seven components of the strategy, namely: 1) the order of elaborative for the main structure of teaching, 2) learning prerequisite sequences (in each subject of the lesson), 3) summary, 4) synthesis, (5) analogy, 6) cognitive and, 7) control of learning.

Prerequisites learning are defined as structures that demonstrate the concepts that must be learned before other concepts. Therefore, it displays the relationship prerequisite for a concept study. Summary of a review of the material that has been studied to maintain retention. Function of summary is to give a brief statement about the material that they have learned and examples of reference that is memorable for each concept. A summary is given at the end of a lesson and just summarize the newly learned material called internal summary, while a summary of all the learning material called external summary.

Pensintesis is a component of theoretical elaboration that serves to show the linkages between the concepts. Pensintesis is very important

because it will give some notions of link between concepts, ease of understanding, increase the meaningfulness to show the context of a concept, giving motivational influence and increase retention.

The analogy is a crucial component in learning for ease of understanding by comparing the new knowledge with the knowledge that has already known to students (Reigeluth and Stein). It is more effective when delivered in early learning.

Learning is designed based on the theory of elaboration is run by seven principles: 1) Presenting learning framework in phases or the first meeting; 2) The parts included into the framework of the content should be in the elaboration gradually; 3) The most important part should be elaborated first; 4) The depth and breadth of elaboration should be optimal; 5) Pensintesis should be given after each time elaborating, 6) Type pensintesis should be tailored to the type of learning content; 7) Summary should be given before each presenting pensintesis.

Merrill (1983) Suggests four forms of presentation, Namely the primary presentation, secondary presentation, display processes presentation, procedures presentation and display presentation. The primary presentation forms is the specificity material and dimensions of students' expectations responsive Comprising: generalitas presentation, examples, ekspositif and inquisitive. It said further that the four primary types of presentations can be in the elaboration with a number of secondary presentation. As for the types of secondary presentation: elaboration prerequisite, additional information on the concepts of components that make up generalitas; Elaboration contextual, additional information such as contextual or historical background. Elaboration mnemonics, memory aids to help students remember.

Cognitivism has several branches of science, including the theory of assimilation, attribution, performance components, elaboration, mental models, and cognitive development. Elaboration theory is a theory about learning design with the basic argument that lessons should be organized from simple materials that led to the expectation that the complex by developing an understanding in a meaningful context that developed into ideas are integrated. This understanding is Formulated by Reigeluth of Indiana University and colleagues in the 1970s. This concept has three key words that focus on the concept of the order of elaboration, theoretical elaboration, and simplification of the conditions.

Learning starts from the simple and easy concept. How to teach thoroughly and deeply, and apply the principles to be more detailed. The principle should be used to approach the topic spiral. A number of concepts and stages of learning to be divided into learning episode. Furthermore, students choose the concept, principle, or a version of the work in the elaboration or studied.

Elaboration approach evolved in tandem with the growing changes in the learning paradigm from teacher-centered becomes a student-centered. This theory also emphasizes the importance of the functions

motivators, analogies, summaries, and syntheses that help improve the effectiveness of learning.

This theory also gives attention to the aspects of complex cognitive and psychomotor learning. The basic idea is that students need to develop the contextual meaning in order to assimilate knowledge and skills.

According Reigeluth (1999), Elaboration theory contains some value, as shown below.

- a. There is a sequence of instructions that cover a whole making it possible to increase motivation and meaningfulness.
- b. Giving the possibility to the students to navigate the various things and decide the order of the learning process in accordance with their wishes.
- c. To facilitate the learning process of students in developing rapidly.
- d. Integrate the various approaches variable according to the design theory.

In the application of elaboration strategi must be based on the material in the form of concepts, procedures, and principles. It is closely related to the process of elaboration of sustainable, involving students in the development of ideas or skills in practical applications. This strategy allows students to add their own ideas to strengthen knowledge.

Teaching materials can be assessed suitability if 1) the right order of the contents, 2) learners' motivation, 3) participation and exercises for learners, 4) provide feedback, 5) the availability of appropriate assessment, 6) have instructions to not further including how to facilitate memory, 7) delivery systems and the media format in accordance with the purpose and context of learning, and 8) the direct instructions for the learner from one activity to the next activity.

A perfect example of this is the learners who have a list of examples of concepts that can be beneficial. The characteristics of Elaboration based learning:

- a. Familiarize learners to read and write through a particular task,
- b. Facilitate learners to bring new ideas through giving tasks,
- c. Provide opportunities for students to think, analyze, solve problems and act without fear,
- d. Cooperative,
- e. healthCompetition
- f. Create a report.

There are seven principles in Elaboration learning model which is as follows:

- a. Presentation of the content framework, which shows the main parts of the main areas of study and the relationship between these parts.
- b. The parts that are covered within the framework of the content will be elaborated gradually.
- c. The most important part is presented first
- d. The depth and breadth of each elaboration will be performed optimally.

- e. Presentation will be done gradually, meaning presentation will be awarded after each time elaborating.
- f. Each presentation be adapted to the content of the field of study.
- g. A summary will be given before next presentation

Furthermore Reigeluth (1983) suggested organizing elaboration of teaching should be done with attention to the steps as follows:

- a. Presentation epitome
- b. Elaboration of the first stage
- c. Providing a summary and synthesis of the parts
- d. Elaboration of the second stage
- e. Summary and final synthesis.

Teaching begins with the presentation of the epitome, by presenting the structure of the content in the form of a general overview of the most basic, most important, and most understandable of course content to be delivered. Then in the elaboration of the first stage, presented descriptions of each section are presented in epitome. Starting from the most important part to another part sequentially. Elaboration of each part of the end with a summary and synthesis of new teaching contents delivered. The next step is the provision of a summary and synthesis of the parts. In this section, the final activity of elaboration of the first stage, a summary of all the parts that are elaborated. Synthesis showing the relationship of the parts that have been elaborated and between parts of the epitome. Further elaboration of the second phase, more detailed elaboration of sub-sections in the elaboration of the first stage is determined by the corresponding depth teaching purposes. Just as the elaboration of the first stage, followed by a second stage of elaboration of learning provision synthesis.

The final step is a summary and synthesis of the final. At this stage presented a synthesis and summary of the overall content in the structure of the lesson.

Thus, it can be concluded that the theoretical elaboration integrate some knowledge of the content structuring strategies that already exist, to create a comprehensive model of how to organize the teaching at the macro level. The elaboration prescribed ways of organizing the contents of a field of study by following the general sequence to detail, starting with displaying epitome, then elaborating the parts contained in the epitome in detail.

C. Research Questions

1. Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who taught by using the Elaboration based-learning method to conventional.
2. Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who have a high motivation taught by using the Elaboration based-learning method and with conventional.

3. Are there significant differences of English learning outcomes between students who have a low motivation taught by using the Elaboration based-learning method and with conventional?.
4. Is there no interaction effect between Elaboration based learning method and motivation towards English learning outcomes?.

D. Research Methodolgy

This research was conducted at the Junior High School of Alfajar, Bekasi, Eastern of Jakarta, Indonesia. The research method used in this research was descriptive quantitative experimental method with independent comparative test sample t test and 2 factorial design x 2 (Sugiyono.20090). The population in this study were all students of first grade of Junior High School of Alfajar. In this case, the author used the total sample as an object of research was homogeneous and there were not too many. The data in this study using a test instrument to test the results of study and a questionnaire for motivation to learn. The questionnaire was based on the form of Likert Scale. It was drawn up in the form of five selection options: Strongly Agree, Quite Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree (Aiken 1994). The research instruments were based on the conceptual definition and operational definition for each variable. The validity and reliability of all instruments were tested before given to the students.

E. Data analysis technique

Testing the Hypothesis was done by using analysis of variance. Categorizing variables implemented by Ideal Mean and Standard Deviation obtained by calculation. then the testing requirements of the data analysis, normality and homogeneity test. Normality test was done using a formula *Kolmogorov-Smirnov*, while homogeneity test was done using *Anova*. Testing Hypothesis was done by testing the comparative independent variables using *t-test* and to influence the interaction between each independent variable on the dependent variable using a 2x2 factorial analysis of variance (Arikunto, 1986),

F. Research results

1. Description Research Data

Data obtained from the results of English posttest in the first grade students of Alfajar_ after the experiment.

Tabel 5
Description Of Posttest Data of Control Class and
Experiment Class
Statistics

		Ktrl	Eksp
N	Valid	37	37
	Missing	37	37
Mean		20,5676	22,2973
Median		21,0000	22,0000
Mode		21,00	18,00 ^a
Std. Deviation		3,05996	3,31549
Variance		9,363	10,992
Range		12,00	12,00
Minimum		15,00	16,00
Maximum		27,00	28,00

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

Data collected on the outcome posttest control classes are described as follows. At posttest control class theoretical score range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 15 to 27, and the range is 12. From the calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 20.56; median = 21; mode = 21; and standard deviation = 3.06. Based on the results of processing (data attached) known to overall respondents to the items incorporated in the posttest control class variables included in the low category, because $\bar{x} < (Mi + 1. SDI)$, or $20.57 < 24.00$. While in the experimental class posttest scores theoretical range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 16 to 28, and the range is 12. From the calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 22.3; median = 22; mode = 18; and standard deviation = 3.31. Based on the results of processing known to overall respondents to items belonging posttest in the experimental class variables included in the enough category, because $(Mi + 1. SDI) > \bar{x} \geq Mi$, or $24 > 22.3 \geq 22$.

Tabel 6
Description of High Motivation Data for Control Class and Experiment Class

Statistics

		Ktrl	Eksp
N	Valid	32	32
	Missing	42	42
Mean		20,3438	21,8750
Median		20,5000	21,0000
Mode		21,00	18,00
Std. Deviation		3,16849	3,25031
Variance		10,039	10,565
Range		12,00	12,00
Minimum		15,00	16,00
Maximum		27,00	28,00

Data collected on the results of high motivation posttest control classes are described as follows. At posttest control class theoretical score range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 15 to 27, and the range is 12. From the calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 20.34; median = 20.5; mode = 21; and standard deviation = 3.17. Based on the results of processing known to overall respondents to the items incorporated in the posttest high motivation variable control classes included in the poor category, because $\bar{x} < (Mi + 1. SDI)$, or $20.34 < 23$. While on posttest high motivation theoretical experimental class score range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 16 to 28, and the range is 12. From the calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 21.88; median = 21; mode = 18; and standard deviation = 3.25. Based on the results of processing was known as a whole answers of respondents to the posttest items incorporated in the experimental class high motivation variables included in the poor category, because $\bar{x} < (Mi + 1. SDI)$, or $21.88 < 24$.

Tabel 7
Description of low Motivation Data for Control Class and
Experiment Class

Statistics		MRdKtrl	MRdEksp
N	Valid	5	5
	Missing	59	59
Mean		22,0000	25,0000
Median		22,0000	26,0000
Mode		22,00	27,00
Std. Deviation		1,87083	2,54951
Variance		3,500	6,500
Range		5,00	6,00
Minimum		19,00	21,00
Maximum		24,00	27,00

Data collected on the results of low motivation posttest control classes are described as follows. At posttest control class theoretical score range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 19 to 24, and the range is 5. The calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 22; median = 22; mode = 22; and standard deviation = 1.87. Based on the results of processing (data attached) known to overall respondents to the items incorporated in the posttest low motivation variable control classes included in the category enough, because $(Mi + 1. SDI) > \bar{x} \geq Mi$, or $22.33 > 22 \geq 21.5$. While in the low motivation posttest experimental class scores theoretical range is between 0 to 29, based on data collected empirically derived scores range between 21 to 27, and the range is 6. From the calculation of basic statistics obtained a mean score = 25; median = 26; mode = 27; and standard deviation = 2.55. Based on the results of processing known to overall respondents to the items incorporated in the posttest low motivation variable experimental class in the high category, because $\bar{x} \geq (Mi + 1. SDI)$, or $25 \geq 25$.

2. Motivation to learn

Data of motivation to learn was obtained from the results of questionnaires on the first grade students of Alfajar Yuniar High School, with a total of 37 respondents, with the number of statements of 20 questions regarding the issue of motivation consisting of four indicators, namely the attitudes, needs, perceptions, and decisions that occur in a person.

Based on the results of data processing, the obtained information that the data is composed of 20 items were tested to first grade students in the form of Likert scale, with a mean total of 3.7716; the average standard deviation of 0.7975; the mean ideal (M_i) of 3.0135; and the standard

deviation of the ideal (S_{di}) of 0.1172; thus the $M_i + 1.SD_i$ is 3.667. Therefore, it can be seen as a whole answers of respondents to the items included in the high category, because $\bar{x} \geq (M_i + 1.SD_i)$, or ≥ 3.7716 3.3667. So quite understand the respondents to a statement filed to the questionnaire, and motivation to learn of first grade Yuniior High School students 1 is high.

Furthermore, from the answers to each of the respondents for 20 items were calculated median to determine the motivation level high and low. And the result is the number of students with low motivation as many as 5 students and high motivation as many as 32 students.

G. Discussion

Based on the results of statistical analysis on the control and experimental classes, showed that results for students in the experimental class was better than students in the control class. This is caused by differences in the application of learning methods, in which the experimental class teaching elaboration methods, while the control class using conventional teaching methods. And other factors that cause progressive increase learning outcomes is the intelligence, talent, interest and attention, motivation to learn, family, and school factors (Crow, at all. 1988). Where if student has been able to meet those factors that tend to be able to obtain learning outcomes, in addition to psychological factors. Thus, students can receive a new experience by implemented elaborations.

The results of the analysis of the hypothesis stated that there was a significant interaction effect between elaboration based learning methods and students' motivation to learn.. While simultaneously there were no significant interaction effect between elaboration based learning method to learning outcomes. However, that application of the elaboration based learning method and motivation to study has Contributed to student's learning outcomes.

This is in accordance with the opinion stated by Sanjaya (2006) that learning was not memorizing facts or information. Learning was done; gained particular experience in accordance with the expected goals. Therefore, learning strategies should encourage student activity. Activities not intended to be limited to physical activity, but also included activities of a psychic nature such as mental activity.

According Degeng (1989), learning designed by Elaboration Theory was run by seven principles: 1) Presenting learning framework in phases or the first meeting; 2) The parts included into the framework of the content should be in the elaboration Gradually; 3) The most important part should be elaborated first; 4) The depth and breadth of elaboration should be optimal; 5) Pensintesis should be given after each time elaborating, 6) Type pensintesis should be tailored to the type of learning content; 7) Summary should be given before each serving pensintesis.

H. Research Conclusions

1. There is a significant difference between students' English learning outcomes by treatment elaboration based-learning method with students treated with conventional teaching method. Judging from their mean values, the group of students who received treatment with elaboration based learning methods mean higher gain than the students treated conventional teaching method. Thus the application elaboration based-learning method obtain better English learning outcomes compared to conventional teaching method.
2. There are significant differences of English learning outcomes of students who have high motivation to learn with elaboration based-learning method compared to learn with conventional method. Judging from the average group of students who have high motivation to learn with elaboration based-learning method obtaining a mean value is higher than the group of students to learn with conventional method.
3. There are significant differences of English learning outcomes of students who have low motivation to learn with elaboration based-learning method compared to learn with conventional method. Judging from the average, the group of students who have low learning motivation to learn with elaboration based-learning method obtaining a mean value is higher than the group of students who have low learning motivation to learn with conventional method.
4. There is no interaction effect between elaboration based-learning method and motivation on learning outcomes, however, there are significant partial interaction between the elaboration based-learning method and motivation to English learning outcomes.

I. Suggestions

1. Perform a research for theoretical studies related to the elaboration based learning method in a comprehensive and logical.
2. Designing a research model with targeted and measurable so that it can be implemented both in the process of problem analysis, both theoretical and statistical.
3. Determine the amount of sample that is proportional, so as to represent the results of analyzes related to the problem in research.
4. Always make contact with the experts of the obstacles or problems encountered in this study, so the results will be better and focused.

REFERENCES

- Aiken, Lewis R. (1994). *Psychological Testing and Assessment*, (Eight Edition). Boston: Allyn and Bacon..
- Arikunto, Suharsimi. *Manajemen Penelitian*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2003.
- Crocker, L.M. & Algina, J. (1986). *Introduction to Classical and Modern Test Theory*. New York: Holt, Rineheart, Winston.
- Crow, L. & A. Crow, *Psikologi Pendidikan*. Surabaya: Bina Ilmu, 1988.
- Degeng, I Nyoman Sodana.(1989). *Ilmu Pengajaran Taksonomi Variabel*. Jakarta: Depdikbud.
- Dick, W., Carey, L., dan Carey, J.O. (2001). *The Systematic Design of Instruction*. Fifth Edition. New York : Longman.
- Nasution, S., *Didaktik Asas-asas Mengajar*, Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 1995, Cet. Ke-1, Ed. 2.
- Purwanto, Ngalim, *Psikologi Pendidikan*, Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosda Karya, 1998.
- Reigeluth, C.M. dan Stein, F.S. (1983). "The Elaboration Theory of Instructional" Dalam C.M. Reigeluth (Ed.). *Instructional–Design Theories and Models: An verview of Their Current Status*. Hillsdale, N.J: Lowrence Erlbaum Associate.
- Sabri, M. Alisuf, *Pengantar Psikologi Umum dan Perkembangan*, Jakarta: CV. Pedoman Ilmu Jaya, 2001.
- Sanjaya, Wina. *Strategi Pembelajaran Berorientasi Standar Proses*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group. 2006.
- Sardiman, A.M, *Interaksi dan Motivasi Belajar Mengajar*. Jakarta: C.V. Rajawali, 1990.
- Slameto, *Belajar dan Faktor-faktor yang Mempengaruhinya*, Jakarta: Rineka Cipta, 2003, Cet. Ke-4.
- Sugiyono, *Statistika untuk Penelitian*, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2009.
- Wahjosumidjo, *Kepemimpinan dan Motivasi*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia, 1987.
- Winkel, WS., *Psikologi Pendidikan dan Evaluasi Belajar*, Jakarta: Gramedia, 1986, Cet. Ke-3.